
Development of Intervention Program for Enhancing General Education Learners' Relationship with Special Needs Education Learners

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Abstract

This study examined the manifestations of behavior of general education learners toward special needs education learners along cognitive understanding, behavioral intent, and affective response; to evaluate an inclusive classroom ambassador program developed through the ADDIE model; and to evaluate the effectiveness of how peer-led interventions could improve behavioral inclusion. A descriptive-evaluative research design was employed and 48 grade four to six learners were involved in a month-long peer-led intervention that included ambassador selection and training, peer cascading, as well as an inclusive awareness day, which occurred over a duration of four weeks, February to March 2025. To measure attitudes prior to and after the program, the Chedoke-McMaster Attitudes Towards Children with Handicaps Scale (CATCH) was used, as well as to identify changes to attitudes, Descriptive Statistics and the Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Test. Results indicated that there was a strong cognitive understanding of special needs education learners at baseline ($M = 2.46$) but that no significant improvement was demonstrated with post-test data ($M = 2.46$, $p = .144$). However, there was a significant improvement in behavioral intent from pre-test ($M = 2.04$) to post-test ($M = 2.36$) ($p < .001$) and that affective response scores increased slightly but not significantly from pre-test ($M = 2.06$) to post-test ($M = 2.11$) ($p = .611$). Overall, the program increased prosocial behavior, peer support and inclusionary, inclusive practices in the classroom, as well as improved student ambassadors' leadership and communication capabilities. However, based on this study, further research is required to continue to fully understand the effectiveness of peer-led inclusion programs in improving behavioral inclusion, and that additional factors may need to be considered such as longer-duration or more intensive interventions to bring about changes to affective attitudes.

Keywords: general education, special needs education, inclusive education

Inclusive education focused on access, participation, and effective learning experiences that reach all learners despite their ability. An integral component of inclusive education is a feeling of belongingness that creates positive friendships, socialization, and learning collaborations among students. In an inclusive classroom setting, effective interactions between Gen Ed and SNED learners may have a positive impact on a

socially responsible and socially just education setting. This is mandated under RA 11650 otherwise known as "Inclusive Education Act" that there is a need to develop an inclusive learning environment.

Learners in the Gen Ed group have shown that they were able to display patience, sympathy, and open-mindedness to help SNED group members (Garrote et al., 2020). Moreover, having positive attitudes about inclusion promoted a peaceful

democracy in a school culture (Euscategui & Saavedra, 2024). Furthermore, evidence-based practices such as peer tutoring and disability awareness were believed to promote peer relationships (Schwab et al., 2021). However, in most classes, evidence-based practices were not well utilized, which means that learners in the SNED group were likely to be socially isolated, whereas the Gen Ed learners will also not have the skills for interacting socially.

Previous research on inclusive education in the Philippines has mainly centered on curriculum development, teacher preparedness, and teaching approaches (Namanyane & Shaoan, 2021; Lin et al., 2025; Echsel et al., 2025). Nevertheless, there is a lack of literature on interventions that foster structured peer relationships within the indigenous classroom setting. This study is a development on previous literature on inclusive education for it has developed an intervention program referred to as the “Inclusive Classroom Ambassadors Program” with the objective of enhancing Gen Ed-SNED interaction, acceptance, and cooperation. Unlike past literature on inclusive education that was based on a structural approach, this study is informed by a social approach that motivated Gen Ed student cognitive understanding, behavioral intentions, and affective response towards their SNED peers.

Research Objectives

The purpose of this study was to analyze, design, develop, implement and evaluate an intervention program that will help to create positive relationship behaviors and social interactions between Gen Ed students toward their SNED peers. Specifically, this study explored learners’ (1) manifestations of behavior along Cognitive Understanding, Behavioral Intent, and Affective Response; (2) designed and implemented an intervention program to enhance learners’ positive relationship

behaviors and social interactions toward their SNED peers; and (3) evaluated the effectiveness of this program in order to determine and assess behavioral changes of participants over the three recognized areas.

Scope and Delimitation

The scope of this study was to develop a program that positively impacts General Education Students’ interactive behavior toward their Special Needs Education (SNED) peers as defined by the ADDIE (Analyze, Design, Development, Implement, Evaluate) Model. The program included specific actions to enhance cognitive understanding, behavioral intention, and affective responses based on an initial pilot evaluation of the current behavior of the participants. The participants included 48 students (24 male and 24 female) from grades 4-6 from Tagkawayan Central Elementary School. The selection process was based on a teacher’s recommendation of behavior, willingness to participate, and frequency of peer interaction. Grades 4–6 were chosen due to learners’ social, cognitive, and emotional maturity to engage meaningfully with SNED peers.

This program is a month-long implementation (February-March) using descriptive-evaluative designs (structured observational and checklist questionnaire), and a descriptive analysis was completed utilizing descriptive statistics and a Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Test for statistical analysis. Limitations include a small Gen Ed participant sample. The study only involved SNED learners with hearing impairments, mild intellectual/learning disabilities and autism spectrum disorder; as well as the specific school context limiting the generalizability of the study. Additionally, the short implementation period and absence of a control group limited the ability to make causal interpretations, and observer and response bias may have impacted study outcomes.

Conceptual Framework

This study utilized Social Cognitive Theory (Bandura, 1986 as cited in Sim et al., 2022; Ying et al., 2023), Contact Theory (Allport, 1954 as cited in Rademaker et al., 2020), and Attitude Formation Theory (Eagly & Chaiken, 1993 as cited in Deng et al., 2024). Social Cognitive Theory explained learning through observation, modeling and reflection and was used to help shape program activities to allow for learners to observe inclusive behaviors and replicate those behaviors during their interactions in the classroom. Contact Theory posited that combining positive, cooperative interactions will reduce prejudice and support acceptance, and this was operationalized through collaborative structured activities between General Education and SNED learners. Attitude Formation Theory suggests that attitudes develop over time through social learning and interaction allowing learners to gradually incorporate a positive attitude towards diversity and working cooperatively together. Together, these theories informed the program design to improve learners' social behaviors, attitudes, and interactions within inclusive classrooms.

Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework illustrated how the ADDIE model is being applied in the development of the Inclusive Classroom Ambassadors Program (See Figure 1).

Analysis phase assessed current behavior of Gen Ed students and existing gaps in knowledge were integral in providing insights for structured objectives, activities, and evaluation strategies for fostering positive behavior and social interactions. The development phase mainly focused on developing training resources, activity guide, and classroom resources for ambassadors. Implementation phase mostly entailed running training sessions, structured peer interactions, and monitoring student behaviors and interactions. Finally, there is

an evaluation of student behavior, peer interactions, and overall program efficacy through pre- and post-test results, observation, and feedback. At the heart of the conceptual framework is the Inclusive Classroom Ambassadors Program, which is integral in promoting positive peer relationships and iterative improvements.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The research design employed was descriptive evaluative, which was selected to assess the current behavior of general education students and evaluate the impact of the Peer Inclusion Network (PIN) - Inclusive Classroom Ambassador Program. The descriptive design portion of the model assessed learners' behavior towards special needs education (SNED) students based on cognitive, behavioral, and affective aspects of their learning, both prior to and after being accepted into the program. The evaluative design portion provided benchmarks for assessing effectiveness of the program, based on comparison between pre and posttest findings.

Respondents/Participants of the Study

The participants were composed of 48 learners from Grades 4 to 6 in General Education from Tagkawayan Central

Elementary School. The respondents were selected based on the method of purposive sampling with consideration of the teachers' recommendations and established criteria for effective and significant participation and response from the learners who qualify based on the following characteristics: bona fide students who manifest interest and willingness to understand the concepts of inclusion and special needs education, manifestations of commitment and intent for promoting inclusion, and possession of communication and leadership attributes.

The grades 4 to 6 were chosen for this study based on the cognitive, social, and emotional abilities of the learners that enabled them to comprehend diversity, have empathy towards others, as well as promote an inclusive culture, since they can participate actively in activities alongside their peers. The equal number of males and females within the chosen grades helped to balance the study sample to avoid any anticipated bias based on gender differences.

Data Gathering Tools

The main data collection instrument utilized was the Chedoke-McMaster Attitudes toward Children with Handicaps (CATCH) Scale. This scale evaluates attitudes in three areas: cognitive understanding, behavioral intentions, and affective response. The data collection instrument was under expert validation for content appropriateness and validation among the intended data subjects. This scale has already been proven valid and reliable in the measurement of attitudes toward children with special needs education (Llanes et al., 2023). The ADDIE model ensured proper data collection, development of the program, and eventually the evaluation of the process in alignment with the study's objectives.

Data Gathering Procedure

This study was anchored to the ADDIE model (Analyze, Design, Develop,

Implement, Evaluate) to systematically plan, implement, and assess the Peer Inclusion Network (PIN): Inclusive Classroom Ambassadors Program. The procedure ensured consistent, reliable, and valid data collection aligned with the research objectives.

Analyze Phase

Baseline data on general education learners' behaviors, social interactions, and attitudes toward SNEd learners were gathered using a structured checklist (CATCH Scale). Results were analyzed to identify prevailing relationship patterns, which informed the design of an evidence-based intervention.

Design Phase

The PIN program was designed based on inclusive education principles, social learning theory, and peer mediation. Structured modules focused on empathy, leadership, communication, and peer support. Interactive and experiential activities were incorporated, and the program was refined through expert and teacher feedback.

Development Phase

Training materials, activity guides, and learning resources were developed and refined based on feedback. Materials were culturally appropriate, learner-centered, and aligned with inclusive values such as empathy, cooperation, and acceptance.

Implement Phase

Selected student ambassadors were trained and deployed as peer facilitators. The program was introduced school-wide (pilot-tested) through Inclusive Awareness Day. Ongoing monitoring by teachers and the researcher ensured fidelity to the program design and allowed timely adjustments.

Evaluate Phase

Post-intervention data were collected using the same checklist to measure changes

in cognitive understanding, behavioral intent, and affective response. Participant feedback and outcome analysis showed improvements in peer acceptance, collaboration, and diversity awareness. Findings supported the program's effectiveness and guided further refinement and potential for wider implementation.

Data Analysis Techniques

The researcher used statistical methods to examine whether general education learners would show measurable differences in their understanding in special needs education learners before and after participating in the Peer Inclusion Network program.

A descriptive statistic was used, which included mean and standard deviation, to measure students' attitudes in Objective 1 which showed both their attitude level and their degree of attitude variation. The mean score represented the overall direction and favorability of attitudes, with higher values indicating more positive dispositions toward SNEd learners. The standard deviation explained how far responses varied from each other because students showed more similar opinions when standard deviation values were small yet they had greater attitude differences between them when standard deviation values were high.

However, Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Test was used to compare pre-test results with post-test results in three domains which included cognitive and behavioral and affective development for Gen. Ed. learners. This non-parametric test was deemed appropriate due to the paired nature of the data and its suitability for measuring changes in the same group of respondents over time. The analysis showed how the PIN intervention affected learners' attitudes toward their peers who received special needs education.

Ethical Considerations

Prior to the actual conduct of the study, approval was secured from the school principal, public school district supervisor, and Schools Division Office to implement the Inclusive Classroom Ambassadors Program in Tagkawayan Central Elementary School in Tagkawayan, Quezon. Participation in the research was undertaken in an agreement with the Data Privacy Act of 2012 (RA 10173). Informed parental consent was secured prior to the involvement of both general education learners and learners with special needs education. In the ethic standards observed in conducting research, voluntary participation, confidentiality of information, and respect and protection of the rights and welfare of the research respondents were observed in the entire length of the research period.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Manifestation of Behavior of General Education Learners

The results showed that the general education learners possessed positive attitudes towards their peers with special needs even before the implementation of the program across cognitive understanding, behavioral intent, and affective response as reflected in the obtained mean scores.

In the cognitive understanding, as shown in table 1, students showed a well-developed and empathetic understanding of the learners with special needs education since, as shown by the mean scores, the students knew that the peers with special needs education were in dire need of support ($M = 3.02$), that these peers enjoy attention from adults ($M = 2.94$), and that the peers with special needs education prefer to be socially involved with the other members of the class rather than staying isolated as shown by the mean score of the students' answers ($M = 2.90$). Most notably, the idea that students with special needs education were

isolated socially was clearly rebuffed by the students ($M = 1.33$).

Table 1. Cognitive Understanding Before Program Implementation

INDICATORS	M	SD	Qualitative Index
Children with special needs education want lots of attention from adults. (Ang mga batang may espesyal na pangangailangan ay nais ng maraming atensyon mula sa mga matatanda.)	2.94	1.01	Very Good
Children with special needs education don't like to make friends. (Ang mga batang may espesyal na pangangailangan ay hindi gustong makipagkaibigan.)	1.33	0.89	Poor
Children with special needs education want to play with other children. (Ang mga batang may espesyal na pangangailangan ay nais maglaro kasama ang ibang mga bata.)	2.90	1.47	Very Good
Children with special needs education need lots of help to do things. (Ang mga batang may espesyal na pangangailangan ay nangangailangan ng maraming tulong upang gawin ang mga bagay.)	3.02	1.67	Very Good
General Mean	2.37	0.42	Unsure

Behavioral intent results showed predominantly positive and prosocial behavioral intentions in Table 2. The highest behavioral intention was related to protective intentions, protecting their classmates with special needs education from teasing, for which the highest mean was obtained ($M = 3.21$). The intention to include their special needs education classmates in a social setting like parties ($M = 2.83$) and parties like lunchtime ($M = 2.81$) was found to be moderate but positive. Moreover, exclusionary behavioral intentions were rejected, as seen from very low means obtained for avoiding introductions to friends ($M = 0.83$). The findings showed that general education students have a positive behavioral intent.

Table 2. Behavioral Intent Before Program Implementation

INDICATORS	M	SD	Qualitative Index
Would stick up for a child with special needs education who was being teased. (Ipagtatanggol ko ang batang may espesyal na pangangailangan na pinagtatawanan.)	3.21	1.08	Excellent
Would invite a child with special needs education to my birthday party. (Ilimitahan ko ang batang may espesyal na pangangailangan sa aking kaarawan.)	2.83	1.10	Very Good
Would not introduce a child with special needs education to my friends. (Hindi ko ipakikilala ang batang may espesyal na pangangailangan sa mga kaibigan ko.)	0.83	1.62	Poor
Would invite a child with special needs education to eat lunch with me. (Ilimitahan ko ang batang may espesyal na pangangailangan na kumain ng tanghalian kasama ko.)	2.81	1.57	Very Good
General Mean	2.04	0.48	Unsure

The positive dispositions of study participants were demonstrated through their affective responses shown on Table 3. Empathy emerged as the strongest emotional indicator, receiving the highest mean score ($M = 3.23$), which researcher assessed as Excellent because it demonstrated authentic emotional comprehension and empathy. Students showed positive feelings about collaborative learning through group projects which received a mean score of 3.00 and they showed positive feelings about social interaction which received a mean score of 2.81. The special needs education students showed readiness to work together with their peers. Students showed maximum fear-based attitudes which produced a mean score of 0.77 that evaluated as Very Poor because it demonstrated an extreme rejection of negative or avoidant emotions. The data indicated that general education students established a strong affective foundation which included acceptance and emotional

security together with openness to inclusive classroom practices.

Table 3. Affective Response Before Program Implementation

INDICATORS	M	SD	Qualitative Index
Would feel good doing a school project with a child with special needs education. (Maganda ang pakiramdam kapag gumawa ng proyekto sa paaralan kasama ang batang may espesyal na pangangailangan.)	3.00	0.87	Very Good
Would be pleased if a child with special needs education invited me to their house. (Ikalulugod na maimbitahan ng isang batang may espesyal na pangangailangan sa kanilang bahay.)	2.81	1.04	Very Good
Would be afraid of a child with special needs education. (Matatakot sa isang batang may espesyal na pangangailangan.)	0.77	1.01	Very Poor
Feel sorry for children with special needs education. (Naiisip ang kalagayan ng mga batang may espesyal na pangangailangan.)	3.23	1.29	Excellent
General Mean	2.06	0.42	Unsure

Design, Develop, and Implement a Program

The Peer Inclusion Network (PIN), an Inclusive Classroom Ambassadors Program, was developed to promote the involvement of students as active participants and supporters of peers with special needs education, creating a culture of inclusion in the school. This was achieved through a systematic approach in the development of the program to include the formulation of the objectives, the activities to be covered, and the outcomes of the program, after which expert opinion was obtained from teachers, administrators, and stakeholders to assess the evaluative criteria of the program. This was done before the final approval by the administrators to ensure compliance.

Ambassadors in the Peer Inclusion Network were selected upon teacher recommendations based on their demonstration of positive social characteristics and leadership potential. Parental consent was gathered in order to maintain ethical standards. These selected students had then undergone systematic training in the tenets of inclusive education, kinds of disabilities, effective communication skills, advocacy, and leadership. Ambassadors then provided peer-led activities and discussions promoting practice dissemination among general education learners. Activities in the PIN program culminated in an Inclusive Awareness Day that promoted school-wide participation in the celebration of diversity. In summary, the PIN program aimed at student leader development who are empathetic, well-informed, and proactive in advocating for inclusive educational settings.

Effectiveness of the Program

The findings have shown differentiated effects of the intervention program in all areas of cognitive, behavioral, and affective domains of general education learners' attitudes toward students with special needs education (SNED).

Table 4 showed a positive level of cognitive understanding of general education learners toward SNED peers, with an overall mean score of 2.46. The result, however, failed to reveal significant changes in cognitive perception levels after conducting a hypothesis test between the pre- and post-program, showing no significant change, with a value of $p = .144$. This has shown that learners generally possess a basic level of cognitive understanding and knowledge of SNED learners' educational needs, but there was no marked improvement in cognitive perception levels of SNED learners following the program, possibly since cognitive perception is generally positive.

Table 4. Cognitive Understanding After Program Implementation

Measurement Period	Mean (M)	SD	Qualitative Index	Mean Difference	z-value	p-value	Interpretation ($\alpha=0.05$)
Before Implementation	2.37	0.42	Moderately Positive	--	--	--	--
After Implementation	2.46	0.29	Moderately Positive	+0.09	-1.462	0.144	Not Significant

In contrast, the program had a strong and statistically significant impact on students' behavioral intentions. This is supported by the following results, which showed on Table 5 that mean scores shifted from 2.04 (SD = 0.48) prior to program implementation to 2.36 (SD = 0.36) after program implementation. The results were statistically significant ($z = -4.549$, $p < .001$) with a large effect size ($r = -0.657$), which confirmed that the program had a significant influence on students' willingness to behave in ways that are positive and supportive towards their fellow students with SNED.

Table 5. Behavioral Intent After Program Implementation

Measurement Period	Mean (M)	SD	Mean Difference	z-value	p-value	Decision ($\alpha = 0.05$)	Effect Size (r)	Magnitude
Before Implementation	2.04	0.48	--	--	--	--	--	--
After Implementation	2.36	0.36	+0.32	-4.549	<.001	Reject Null (Significant)	-0.657	Large

The affective response demonstrated a "Moderately Positive" attitude at the beginning ($M = 2.06$, $SD = 0.42$), as reference to Table 6. This level improved slightly after the program ($M = 2.12$, $SD = 0.22$). While the difference was not significant ($z = -0.508$, $p = 0.611$), the sharp decrease in the standard deviation suggested a more cohesive level of emotions among the learners. This essentially speaks to a more uniform empathy within the classroom, regardless of the lack of significant increase overall. Thus, the aggregate of the data suggested the program was most successful at reinforcing intentions in the behavioral domain and the learners' emotions, while their level of cognition was unaffected.

Table 6. Affective Response After Program Implementation

Measurement Period	Mean (M)	SD	Qualitative Index	Mean Difference	z-value	p-value	Interpretation ($\alpha=0.05$)
Before Implementation	2.06	0.42	Moderately Positive	--	--	--	--
After Implementation	2.12	0.22	Moderately Positive	+0.06	-0.508	0.611	Not Significant

CONCLUSIONS

1. General education learners demonstrated three positive tendencies through their cognitive understanding and their supportive behavioral intent and their affective responses toward peers with special needs education. The participants showed three positive traits through their minimal negative stereotypes and their strong protective behaviors and their willingness to accept others, but they showed less active engagement in social activities. The

study results show that schools have a strong foundation in cognitive and behavioral and emotional skills that help them create better inclusive practices.

2. The intervention program developed in the study was called a Peer Inclusion Network (PIN): Inclusive Classroom Ambassadors Program. This intervention program was effectively designed, developed and implemented in the study. The cascading activities and training sessions encouraged the school community to be more inclusive towards special needs education learners. The intervention program proved that student-led activities can create a sense of responsibility and empathy among the school community towards special needs education learners.
3. The program showed little impact on cognitive understanding because learners maintained their existing positive perceptions of their knowledge after the program ended, which showed the need for specific teaching methods. The study results showed significant growth in behavioral intentions through positive attitudes because they led to people taking part in inclusive activities. The program created positive emotional responses among participants, and its shared emotional climate for inclusion purposes became more stable through decrease in emotional response differences.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. The cognitive awareness and supportive behaviors and positive affective attitudes of general education learners toward their peers who require special needs education

demonstrate the necessity for schools to implement inclusive educational methods through specific comprehensive school improvement strategies. The school environment enables students to interact with each other through organized activities which include integrated peer activities and inclusive student organizations and collective learning tasks and learning spaces that all students can access. The instructional staff needs to demonstrate inclusive teaching methods and empathetic behaviors while they create chances for students to work together and build relationships during both classroom time and recreational periods and they should implement activities that help students develop their social-emotional understanding. Social-emotional learning should be incorporated throughout educational policies together with resources that include assistive technology and trained personnel and recognition of exceptional inclusive practices. Future research should examine how empathy-building strategies and peer mentoring translate into sustained social engagement, how protective and supportive behaviors develop over time, and how contextual factors shape inclusive practices to build a fully inclusive, socially connected school environment.

2. The Peer Inclusion Network (PIN) Program is recommended for implementation at the school-wide level as a peer-based approach to encourage inclusive behavior among learners with SNED. The program should be incorporated into the school's programs for student leadership and values formation. Monitoring and evaluation should be done regularly.

3. The current cognitive understanding of students shows limited progress which requires special educational initiatives that use extended methods to achieve academic success through complete educational programs that include specific teaching methods and assessment methods and continuous teacher education programs. The evidence of improved positive behaviors demonstrates that systematic inclusion programs bring value when they become part of regular school operations because teacher modeling and sufficient resources and professional development and school goal alignment enable their successful implementation while research needs to study their long-term effectiveness. The program needs to extend its duration because students showed modest emotional advancements but their emotional consistency improved through the program together with reflective activities and empathy development and social-emotional learning practices and research on effective program elements.

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